

F·A·A·M facility for airborne atmospheric measurements

FLIGHT FOLDER

Flight No.: B115
 Date: 22 Jul 2005
 Take Off: 10:48:10
 Landing: 15:19:03
 Flight Time: 4h30m53s

Campaign: UTLS CIRRUS 6 (Cirrus cloud microphysics and chemistry Option 1)
Trials Instructions:
Operating Area: SW Approaches

POB	Position	Name	Institute
1	Captain	Alan Roberts	Directflight
2	Co-pilot	Charlie Whittaker	Directflight
3	CCM	Sue Angold	Directflight
4	Mission Scientist	Keith Bower	Manchester University
5	Flight Manager	Stephen Devereau	FAAM
6	CCM2/Cloud Physics	Jim Crawford	FAAM
7	Core chemistry	Alan Woolley	FAAM
8	CCN	Hugh Coe	Manchester University
9	AMS	Gerard Capes	Manchester University
10	ADA/CPI	Martin Gallagher	Manchester University
11	WAS	Maria Nielsdottir	UEA
12	SID2	Edwin Hirst	Hertfordshire
13	SID2	Richard Greenaway	Hertfordshire
14	PTRMS	Anne Hulse	UEA
15	PTRMS	Jennifer Murphy	UEA
16	NOxy	Dave Stewart	UEA
17			
18			
19			
20			

FLIGHT SUMMARY

Flight No B115
 Date: 22nd July 2005
 Project: CIRRUS
 Location: SW Approaches

Start Time	End Time	Event	Height (s)	Hdg	Comments
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104020		start taxi	0.23 kft	129	
104810		T/O	0.0 kft		
105720		JW zero complete	10.0 kft	245	
110037		Nev zero complete	10.0 kft	248	
110609		start lwr BBR test	10.0 kft	247	extend shutter
110929		extend shutter	10.0 kft	257	
111001		retract shutter	10.0 kft	257	
111145		extend shutter	10.0 kft	257	
111203		start video	10.0 kft	257	RFC & DFC
111300		retract shutter	10.0 kft	261	
111422		extend shutter	10.0 kft	258	
111521		end NOxy cal	10.0 kft	260	
111557		retract shtr	10.0 kft	259	
111946		change video	10.0 kft	254	to FFC, RFC
112818	114806	Profile 1	10.0 - 28.0 kft	237	
114902	115904	Run 1.1	28.0 kft	278	
120149	120356	Profile 2	28.1 - 30.0 kft	093	
120356	121352	Run 1.2	30.0 kft	086	
121607	121906	Profile 3	30.0 - 32.0 kft	255	
121945		Nev zero	32.0 kft		
121945	122945	Run 1.3	32.0 kft	293	
123325	123604	Profile 4	32.1 - 33.0 kft	082	
123636	124638	Run 1.4	33.0 kft	089	contrail
124903	125058	Profile 5	33.1 - 34.0 kft	279	
125059	130737	Run 1.5	34.0 kft	275	contrail
131021	131314	Profile 6	34.1 - 35.0 kft	097	
131314	132311	Run 1.6	35.0 kft	096	contrail
132545	133650	Run 1.7	33.0 kft	279	
133952	134826	Run 1.8	31.0 kft	102	
135029		Nev zero	29.0 kft		
135029	141030	Run 1.9	29.0 - 29.1 kft	287	
141305	143507	Run 1.10	27.0 kft	085	
145104	150650	Run 1.11	10.0	073	cal for NOxy
145340		stop video	10.0 kft	077	
151903		Land	0.28 kft	357	

B115 Track 22-JUL-05

Sortie Brief UTLS CIRRUS 6 (Cirrus cloud microphysics and chemistry Option 1)

Flight Number B115

Date 22nd July 2005

Mission Scientist: Keith Bower

Sortie Aims: To make measurements of the microphysics of cirrus clouds and of their interaction with local aerosol and oxides of nitrogen. To investigate the effects of precipitation from the cloud on the vertical distribution of aerosol and oxidized nitrogen

Sortie Location: SW approaches in layers of cirrus ahead of approaching front

Sortie Summary: The aircraft will initially make a vertical profile from well below cloud base to above the top of the cirrus. It will then make a series of straight and level runs of 10 minutes duration at several altitudes below, in and, when possible, above the cloud top. The straight and level runs above and below cloud will concentrate on determining the gaseous composition and aerosol physical and chemical properties of the air. Measurements of the vertical wind velocity will be made here. A straight and level run will be made very close to cloud base to determine whether supercooled water droplets or ice crystals are being activated.. Runs progressively deeper into the cloud will then be flown. SLRs will also be made in the fall streaks from the cirrus to characterise the precipitation in this region and to investigate the influence of the evaporation of the precipitation on the aerosol properties and trace gases in the region of the fall streaks. Advantage will also be taken to fly in and make measurements of any aircraft contrails (and fall streaks from contrails) found in the region (same approach as for natural Ci) .

Sortie Detail

- a. T+0 Take off and climb to FL120 for transit to operating area (with appropriate time [~20mins] - spent at FL100 for NO_x calibration)
- b. T+40 Perform vertical profile ascent P1 through cirrus from below cloud base to aircraft ceiling (fuel load dependant), or to above Ci top whichever is the lower (1000ft/min).
- c. T+60 Descend (not profile descent) to below base of cirrus generating cells and perform straight and level run (SLR) parallel to the mean wind direction 300 feet below cloud base for 10 minutes.
- d. T+75 Turn through 180 degrees. Ascend to cloud base and perform straight and level run for 10 minutes just in cloud at the base of the generating cells. Deviations from the straight run may be made in order to penetrate generating cells provided such penetrations can be achieved with wings level.
- e. T+90 Turn through 180 degrees ascend to middle of cloud and perform SLR for 10 min
- f. T+105 Turn through 180 degrees and if possible ascend to above cloud top and perform straight and level run duration 10 minutes above cloud top
- g. T+120 Descend to below cirrus base and make level runs through fall streaks adjusting flight path to pass through fall streaks as required.
- h. T+135 Descend to lowest altitude reached by fall streaks and make and level runs through the residue.
(NB order of SLRs c-h may be changed by mission scientist to h-c if considered appropriate)
- i. Repeat items b to h as time permits (including profile P2 to above P1 ceiling if failed to get above cloud top in P1)
- j. T+260 return transit (with appropriate time spent at appropriate altitude for NO_x cal)
- k. T+300 Land

Sortie Title UTLS Cirrus 4 (Cirrus cloud microphysics and chemistry Option 1)

Scientific Aims:

1. To measure the total number of Condensation Nuclei (CN), CCN, IN* and the size distribution of optically active particles in clean and polluted air in the UTLS region over the UK. Assessment of their spatial distribution and their likely source based on tracer measurements and air mass history.
2. To quantify the extent to which air mass history, and gas and particle loading can affect the microphysical properties of cirrus clouds in the UTLS region, in particular, the size distribution, phase and morphology of cloud particles.
3. To obtain estimates of HNO₃ loss to cirrus clouds and the subsequent effect on the aerosol population after the cloud has evaporated using case studies involving one or more wave clouds.
4. To make observations of the number, size distribution, phase and morphology of droplets and crystals in cirrus cloud and the number and size distribution of interstitial particles and correlate these with measurements of tracers that identify anthropogenic influence. Hence building on objective 3 to investigate the influence of cirrus on the distribution of aerosol and gases in the UTLS region as cloud and precipitation evaporate.
5. To make an assessment of the chemical composition of the particulate in the UTLS region as a function of their size, their spatial variability and the effect different sources have on their composition.
6. To use measurements of the masses of key components as a function of size of cirrus particle dry residues and interstitial particles to determine if there are distinct chemical differences between activated and unactivated particles.
7. To establish the partitioning of oxidised nitrogen between the gas and aerosol phases as a function of air mass history and source region

Weather conditions

Cirrus cloud preferably associated with the polar front jet preferably over the UK.

Key Measurements

All instruments to be operated continuously.

1) Cloud Physics

- FFSSP, 2DC, 2DP, PCASP, SID-1 and SID-2*. Normal monitoring to ensure correct operation. Operator should note particular features of interest eg. high concentrations, appearance of pristine ice crystal habits etc.
- ADA/CPI – as above
- CCN - alleviator should be filled whilst in clear air either below, between or upwind of the cloud layer(s) of interest. 1 sample per run, if possible.
- J-W LWC and Nevzorov LWC/TWC. Where run is only partially in cloud and starts in clear, these should be zeroed/calibrated and logged by Flight Manager.
- TWC – initial profile should avoid cloud, if possible, to achieve good calibration.

2) FWVS – Switch off the lamp when frost point rises above -15C. Calibration should be performed following altitude changes.

3) WAS - 2 bottle samples per 10min flight leg unless otherwise notified by the Mission Scientist.

- 4) AMS - to be operated on Rosemount inlet. The inlet should be kept closed to avoid contamination whilst the GPU is operating prior to takeoff. It may be opened once the GPU has been removed. Similarly, intake should be closed before GPU is started post-flight.
- 5) Video – the default recording setup should be forward and rear. Flight manager or Flight Scientists should monitor rearward video and inform Mission Scientist of any occurrences of contrail formation (or cessation) and these should be noted in log sheets.

Mission Scientist's Log

M. Sci. Keith Bower

CIRRUS 6

Flight No **B.115**.....

Date **22/07/05**.....

Page **1** of **5**

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
11:48:13	BS7				T10
11:49:21	BS7				CB 1700'
11:50:52	BS7	5000'			landing
11:52:41	BS7				CT 6000'
					cloud - intermittent 6000-6600'
11:55:00	BS7	10000'			NO ₂ cal can start
11:01:20	≡ 12:01:24			BS7 (KN3)	time check.
					temp now in MORACE (screen) GMT
11:13:03	Cals	FL100	259°	51.6N/24W	2.83°C / -14.29°C 11m/s/352° 696mb 261kt
11:13:25					AMS filter run complete.
11:15:25					NO ₂ cal complete HNO ₃ channel holding up
11:28:00					2 photos of Ci ahead
11:28:17	PI start				Profile ascent to 24000
11:34:25	PI	15500	238	51.0/4.6W	-8.52 / -14.47 9m/s/316° 541mb 285kt
12:36:33	PI	FL200	237	50.8/5.1W	-17.94 / -25.47 456mb 7m/s/293° 304kt
11:40:24	PI				CI band directly above us
11:41:00	PI				Photo 6 to LHS
11:41:40	PI				Photo 7 to LHS
11:42:30	PI	FL240			Now in gap - No Ci above, Ci ahead
11:43:56	PI	25250'	(329)	50.6/5.6	Old contrail above
11:44:28	PI				will reduce climb rate as a/c struggles.
11:45:24	PI	26400			Photo 8 ahead
11:46:50	PI				Landing end LHS - CPI 1st Ice Xhd seen
11:47:10	PI	27500			light contrailing (from 146)
11:48:06	PI end	28000	239		end PI turning right onto 290 - mean wind dir in

CB & Ci ahead in this altitude

Mission Scientist's Log

M. Sci: Keith Bower

CIRUS 6

Flight No **B.115**.....

Date 22/07/05.....

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
11:49:02	R1	FL280	280	50.4/6.2	under under edge of Ci sheet
11:51:32	R1	FL280	284		Core Chem Cell - dmy -35.23/-36.2°C
11:52:55	R1	FL280	284	50.4/6.7	329 mb 34 kts 15 m/s / 281°
11:54:20	R1	FL280	283		Photo 9 LMS, at end of
					(Stable descent ^{corrected} turns - corrected for alt/spd etc.)
11:58:10	R1	FL280	283	50.6/7.5	CEN - completed spectrum.
11:59:03	R1 end	FL280			328 mb -34.7/-34.13°C 16 m/s / 239°
					CPI - seen some plubs / small irregulars
12:01:49	P2 start	29.3 NH	92	50.4/7.4	climbing to FL300, 11 m/s / 266° -36.84/-35.53
12:03:51	P2 end	FL300	86	50.4/7.6	R1.2 start -40.05/-39.02°C 9 m/s / 270° 300 mb
					lots 2DC images - grapsed! since end
					CPI - irregular 100-200 μm
12:08:00	R2 1.2	FL300			Below cloud now - heading towards hill streaks
					(cloud sloping up away from us - lower CB behind us.)
12:11:12	R2 1.2	FL300	86	50.5/6.0	-39.88°/-48.49°C 10 m/s / 315° 300 mb
12:13:00	R2 1.2	FL300			CEN spectrum complete
12:13:51	end R1.2	FL300			Will turn and climb to FL320
					SO ₂ flow gone to zero - altitude.
12:16:07	P3	FL300-320			CPC ~ 300-400 cm ³ (AMS)
12:19:07	end P3	FL320			
12:19:45	R1.3 st	FL310	297		CPI seeing ice again 275 mb 22/301°
12:21:22	R1.3	FL320	296	50.3/6.2	-45.6/-49.2
12:23:35					CPI saturated, changed
12:24:57					2DC ~ 120-150 lib ⁻¹ 2DP ~ 150,000

2DC small ice / grapsed.

Mission Scientist's Log

M.Sci KERRY BOWEN

Circus 6

Flight No **B**.....115.....

Date22/07/05.....

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
12:25:30	R1.3	FL320	293	50.5/6.8W	-45.55/-44.4°C 21m/s/281' 274mb 357kt
12:28:40					CPI - saw old Bullet Rosette. 20s ago
12:29:45	R1.3end				turn left - recaptured - dumb b FL340
12:33:19	P4 st	FL320-340	51	50.5/7.0W	372kt 16mb/277° -46.75/-44.69 268mb
12:36:04	en P4	FL330	80	50.6/6.6	not enough performance - stopping P4.
12:36:36	st R1.4	FL330	9		CCN eating sandwich.
12:38:12	R1.4	FL330	44	50.6/6.3	-46.55/-48.08° 18m/s/276° 261mb 367kt mixed bag - Xhals
12:40:50	R1.4	FL330			low cirrus - small ice 2DC ~ 10, 1hr - 30 even dens - small cir.
12:41:25	R1.4	FL330			dear asked - Eastern edge of track.
12:43:30	R1.4	FL330			CPI alt continues to drop
12:44:30	R1.4	FL330	94	50.5/5.3	Bm/s/288 50.5/5.3W -48.96/-50.76 261mb
12:45:10	R1.4				CCN - sample run - very few CCN very few actinobacteria below 1% SS
12:46:36	end R1.4	FL330			turning LH7.
12:49:04	PS	FL330-340	276	50.6/4.9W	statal profile 30 prob
12:50:50	end PS	start R1.5 at FL340	275	50.6/5.1	O ₃ very up and down - 80 prob now / on ground
12:52:00					Contrail - forming behind
12:53:00	R1.5	FL340			CPI nose cone T = +60 checked
13:00:00	R1.5	FL340	275	50.7/6.4W	-51.69/-49.72°C 29m/s/280' 249mb 385kt
13:02:00					CPI measuring - temps all -ve cold. slv problem - wrong readings on alt - in low pres

90 mins -
after
34000
35000
1 hour left

1 hr left

Mission Scientist's Log

M. Sci: KEITH BOWEN

CIRWS 6

Flight No **B.115**.....

Date 22/07/05.....

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
13:04:40	R1.5	FL 340	275		ZDC + SID 1 good data - back in cloud
13:07:38	R1.5 end	FL 340		50.7/7.5	
13:10:20	P6	FL 340-350	99	50.6/7.3	15 m/s / 264° -51.88 / -48.9 245 mb
13:13:10	P6 end	FL 350			see BRossels + photo Rossella in PB - CPI
13:14:55	R1.6	FL 350	95	50.5/6.6	-53.77 / -52.54°C 17 m/s / 277° 236 mb 347 kts
13:21:40	R1.6	FL 350	92	50.4/5.3	near CT. as gain East. -54.1 / -52.9 K/mc / 286'
13:23:11	R1.6 end	FL 350	96	50.4/5.2	descent to FL 330
13:25:37	R1.2 st	FL 330	277	50.6/5.7	-48.47 / -51.17 out of eastern end of cloud 261 mb
					350 kts 23 m/s / 291°
13:27:40	R1.7				getting into edge of cloud.
					chain aggregates - plates - irreg Rossels - side
13:31:50	R1.7	FL 330	275	50.6/6.1W	plates - CPI (Temps OK now)
					-48.38°C / -46.76°C 20 m/s / 275° 261 mb
13:36:50	R1.7 end	FL 330	272	50.6/6.7	descending LT to FL 310
					chains, BR + odd plate - CPI
13:38:35					descending to FL 310
13:39:51	R1.8 st	FL 370	101	50.5/6.5V	-42.3 / -43°C 14 m/s / 273 286 mb 318 kts
					Out of cloud Photos 12, 13, 14 (12 ring/worms cloud ed
13:48:24	R1.8 end	FL 310		50.4/5.1W	Below cloud at this eastern end - v little CCN
13:50:27	R1.9 st	FL 290	282	50.5/5.2W	17 m/s / 311° -37.9 / -42.8°C 313 mb 341 kts
13:52:50	R1.9	FL 290	289	50.5/5.5	Photo 15 RHS (shard of CB)
					Centred on RHS - brown + fall streaks
13:57:15	R1.9				large aggs - plate 200-300, spherical - small et - CPI
					as just going into cloud
14:04:00	R1.9				CPI on continuous trigger aggs

330
310
290

Mission Scientist's Log

M. Sci : KEITH BOWER

CIRRUS 6

Flight No **B.115**.....

Date ...22/07/05.....

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
14:10:29	R1.9 end	FL 290		50.9/7.6W	descending to FL 270 - at Western end/track
14:13:03	R1.10 start	FL 270	83	50.8/7.5W	20 m/s / 263° -32.42/-31.5°C 343 mb
14:17:54	R1.10	FL 270	69	50.9/6.6W	2DC - 150/1hr, 344 mb -32.3/-31.5° 15 m/s / 262°
14:22:30	R1.10	FL 270	70		v large Ag Plate, large + small round 1/2 300-340 μm → smaller ag.
14:24:15	R1.10			51.2/5.5	Out of cloud now
14:26:					Contract ahead
14:28:08					Below - contract (?) - contains K-H billow on top - also is brownish
14:29:42	R1.10	FL 270	69	51.3/5.0W	CCN - not much there -33.36/-33.17°C 8 m/s / 263° 343 mb 320 lbs
14:35:09	R1.10 end	FL 270		51.5/4.2W	AMS CRC - Hnd ~ 5000
14:47:20	Trans ↓		62	51.8/2.8W	Descending from FL 170 - FL 100
14:51:03	Cals	FL 100	77	51.9/2.4W	NOxy calcs - AMS Z.P. Filter CFI problem?
15:04:49					AMS like run - manual save done - now auto saving
15:06:05					NOXY calcs completed
16:10:15	B57	5800			Cloud Top.
16:11:30	B57	4800			CB 1 st layer - multilayer?
16:12:30	B57	3500			CTops at SCu layer - broken
16:18:28	B57	900'			CBase much. base.
16:19:10	B57				Landed..

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG

Flight No. B115

Date: 22/7/05

Operator: jim crawford

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G.M.T. DRS Time	PCASP		FSSP	SID1	2D2-C			2D2-P			Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block Transfer	Particle Count	Conc/L	Max Size	Habit	Conc/m3	Max Size	Habit	
11:37:00											Took this long to get the log working!!!
11:48:00											Sid2 running
114902											Run1
115000	13	0.22	928	0	0	0		0	0		
11:52:00	13	0.33	928	0	0	0		0	0		
11:54:00	13	0.3	928	0	0	0		0	0		
11:56:00	29	2.74	929	100	42	275	10	123	225		
115800	518	0.65	933	500	105	250	10	6000	0		
120100											P2
1202	1100	0.24	942	300	261	225	10	1100			FI290
120400	493	0.79	944	300	128	225	10	1541	0		
120600	12	0.07									
120800	15	0.08	946	0	0	0		6250	0		
121000	25	0.28	946	0	0	0		7475	0		
121200	22	0.43	946	0	0	0		25666			
121400											End r1.2
											P3
121730	20	0.07	946	0	0	0		37000	0		FI310
122000	6	0.09	946	20	2.5	0	10	170000	0		
122200	12	0.07	946	10	22	150	10	242000	0		
122500	115	0.34	948	100	96	200	10	136000	0		
122700	12	0.21	949	100	88	175	10	765000			
122900	20	0.7	950	100	234	200	10	70000			End run1.3

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG

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Date: 22 July 2005

Operator:jim crawford

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G.M.T. DRS Time	PCASP		FSSP	SID1	2D2-C			2D2-P			Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block Transfer	Particle Count	Conc/L	Max Size	Habit	Conc/m3	Max Size	Habit	
123550	213	0.7	957	100	165	175	10	37000			P4 FI330
											R1.4
123700	18	0.04	958	70	9	0	10	1433			
123900	66	0.19	959	100	35	175	10	439			
124100	5	0.09	959	10	0.5	0	0	0			
124300	5	0.1	959	0	0	0		0			
124600	10	0.07	959	0	0	0		0			
											R1.5
125100	11	0.09	959	0	0	0		0			
125300	10	0.07	959	0	0	0		0			
125500	13	0.11	959	0	0	0		0			
125700	33	0.96	959	100	157	175	10	0			
125900	60	0.09	960	200	32	150	10	0			
130100	10	0.4	961	300	110	125	10	0			
130300	37	0.65	964	500	145	200	10	0			
130500	53	0.5	966	300	170	175	10	0			
130700	29	0.7	968	500	163	175	10	0			
											R1.6
131400	41	0.95	971	100	157	150	10	0			
131600	52	0.75	974	800	173	175	10	0			
131800	98	0.8	975	500	106	150	10	0			
132000	73	0.57	977	300	57	150	10	0			
132200	67	0.58	978	30	33	150	10	0			
											R1.7
132600	11	0.14	978	5	10	125	11	0			

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG

Flight No. B117

Date: 22 July 2005

Operator: jim crawford

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G.M.T. DRS Time	PCASP		FSSP	SID1	2D2-C			2D2-P			Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block Transfer	Particle Count	Conc/L	Max Size	Habit	Conc/m3	Max Size	Habit	
132800	27	0.71	978	100	4.5	0		0			
133000	11	1.02	979	200	144	150	11	0			
133200	243	0.9	980	300	204	150	11	0			
133400	72	0.5	982	800	273	225	10	0			
133600	176	0.57	983	300	201	275	10	0			
											R1.8
134000	138	0.69	986	200	227	275	10	0			
134200	156	0.29	988	300	179	250	10	0			
134400	25	0.76	989	200	142	225	10	0			
134600	64	0.93	990	200	132	175	10	483			
134800	5	0.11	991	0	0	0		0			
											R1.9
135100	5	0.15	991	0	0	0		36100			
135300	14	0.07	991	0	0	0		120000			
135500	12	0.08	991	0	0	0		133000			
135700	20	0.37	991	200	64	300	10	140000			
135900	13	0.47	994	100	104	325	10	78000			
140100	21	0.76	996	200	175	275	10	64000			
140300	249	0.47	999	200	149	308	10	74000			
140500	139	1.0	1002	200	227	250	10	40000			
140700	77	0.9	1005	200	147	250	10	60000			
140900	143	0.97	1009	100	87	350	10	58000			
											R1.10
141400	385	1.0	1013	300	122	300	10	18000			
141600	300	0.75	1015	200	105	375	10	26600			
141800	255	0.95	1019	200	121	325	10	26000			
142000	19	0.35	1022	200	113	200	10	2000			
142200	300	0.92	1025	100	36	350	10	11000			

CLOUD PHYSICS PROCESSING LOG**Flight number:** B115**Date:** 22/07/2005

A) FFSSP PROCESSING		
Processing Stage	Completed	Comments
1) Transfer *.txt files from DVD to PC B115_FFSSP_hh.txt for each hour of data B115_FFSSP_HVMS.txt		
2) FTP the files (ascii) from the PC to the directory PMSDATA: on FLOODS	21/10/05	
3) RUN MRFB:[PMS.FAST_FFSSP]FFSSP_EXTRACT_TAS a) Flight number: B115 b) Path name: MFDDATA:B115_MFDX c) Output directory: PMSDATA: d) Start time: 0 if unknown e) End time: 240000 if unknown	24/10/05	
4) RUN MRFB:[PMS.FAST_FFSSP]FFSSP_PROCESS_TXT a) Flight number: B115 b) Directory: PMSDATA: c) TAS in processing: Y d) Vel threshold (clicks) 0 e) Calibration file: Use the most recent calibration file. Format FFSSP_CALddmmyyyy.txt Calibration files to be stored in MRFB:[PMS.FAST_FFSSP]	0 25/10/05	Note the calibration file used FFSSP_CAL15072005.TXT
5) In PVWAVE a) enter: !path=!path+',mrfb:[pms.proc]' Note that the comma before "mrfb" is important! b) write_procffssp_to_m5,'pmsdata:B115_procffssp.dat', 'mfddata:B115_mfdX','pmsdata:B115_m5procffssp',/auto 1st argument is output file from 5) 2nd argument is the MFD 3rd argument is the new FFSSP data file in M5 format c) exit	25/10/05	complete
6) MODIFY a) Modifying datasets: pmsdata:B115_m5procffssp b) Datset: mfddata:B115_mfdX c) New dataset: Enter updated MFD name d) Parameter description file: leave blank to use default	25/10/05	complete

b) Flight number: B115 c) Enter date: YYYYMMDD d) Enter start time 0 if unknown e) Enter end time 240000 if unknown f) Enter time interval (sec) between successive imaged blocks 10 iv) exit PVWAVE Creates files	20	2D-P images not kept
ftp *.PS files from PMSDATA: to PC	PMSDATA:	FAAM_YYYYMMDD_R0_B115_2Dx_IMAGES.PS
Load each into Ghostview or other pdf-converter		O:/Core cloud physics
Output as pdf file (70 dpi resolution) and append name prefix of CORE-CLOUD-PHY_ to converted files		
9) run MRFB:[PMS.SPEC2D.AUTO]PROCESS2D_AUTO		
a) Flight number: B115 b) Directory: PMSDATA: c) File generation: Hit enter d) Time correction: Time offset of the 2D data 0	0	No time offset noted in CP log
e) TAS: Y f) MFD directory: MFDDATA:B115_MFDX g) Probe number: (1) 2DC (2) 2DP (0) Both 0 unless either probe known to be faulty h) Start time: 0 if unkdown i) End time: 240000 if unknown j) Nominal averaging: 0.2 seconds for conversion to M5 k) Particle type: 8 if known to be in ice cloud 11 if known to be in water cloud 8 if known to be in mixed-phase 8 if unknown l) Coefficient choice: 2 m) Output root filename: PMSDATA:B115_PROC2D	1 104800 151900 0.2 8 21/10/05	2DP not processed Note the particle type Ran to completion
10) In PVWAVE		
i) enter: !PATH=!PATH+',MRFB:[PMS.PROC]' Note that the comma before "mrfb" is important! ii) WRITE_PROC2D_TO_M5, 'PMSDATA:B115_PROC2D.DAT', 'PMSDATA:B115_M5PROC2D' iii) exit	21/10/05	
11) MODIFY		
a) Modifying datasets: pmsdata:B115_m5proc2D b) Datset: mfddata:B115_mfdX c) New dataset: Enter modified MFD name d) Parameter description file: leave blank to use default	25/10/05	

CLOUD PHYSICS PROCESSING LOG**Flight number:** B115**Date:** 22/07/2005

C) PCASP PROCESSING		
Processing Stage	Completed	Comments
1) Complete stage 7) in 2D processing Ensures B115_FSP.DAT containing raw PCASP data is written to directory PMSDATA:		
2) run MRFB:[PMS.PCASP]PROCPCASP_NEW a) Flight number: B115 b) File name: PMSDATA:B115_FSP.DAT c) Root output name: PMSDATA:B115_PROCPCASP Produces PMSDATA:B115_PROCPCASP.DAT (binary) PMSDATA:B115_PROCPCASP.OUT (ascii) d) Minimum size channel: Default = 1 If smallest size channel are known to be noisy the value of the highest noise free channel to be entered here e) Calibration volume flow rate: Use the most recent value. Calibration files to be stored in ????? Entering zero gives default value = 1.0 cm ³ /sec f) Time correction: Same value as used in 2D processing stage 9 d) g) Start time: 0 if unknown h) End time: 240000 if unknown	1 1.0 1 0 104800 151900	Note the min size channel Note the volume flow rate
3) In PVWAVE i) enter: !PATH=!PATH+',MRFB:[PMS.PROC]' Note that the comma before "mrfb" is important! ii) write_procpcasp_to_m5,'pmsdata:B115_procpcasp.dat' ,pmsdata:B115_m5procpcasp' iii) exit	25/10/05	
4) MODIFY a) Modifying datasets: pmsdata:B115_m5procpcasp b) Dataset: mfddata:B115_mfdX c) New dataset: Enter modified MFD name d) Parameter description file: leave blank to use default	MFDB 25/10/05	complete

Flight No B115

CCNC LOG

Exp. NC

T/O @ 10:47:10Z

Date 22/07/05

Page 1 of

ALLEVIATOR GMT		Height	Dyn	STATIC						REMARKS
ON	OFF			1	2	3	4	5		
RUN 1.1		24.2		1.75	2.5	3.5	4.25	5.5		
11:49:10	11:49:35	FL280	24.3	0.70	0.76	1.05	1.39	2.03	S	
		RUN 1		2201	2201	2136	2187		D	
				467	467	1003	1025	1078	B	
				2086	2056	2071	2079	2083	R	
				826	826	827	827	826.8	P	
RUN 2										
12:05:15		FL300	23.0	0.48	0.74	1.06	1.58	1.90	S	PEAK NOT FOUND ON 1
12:05:45			23.9	1249	2835	1796	2154	2214	D	2, 3, 4, 5 OK
				886	945	1001	1001	1134	B	
				2002	2019	2023	1994	2019	R	
				806.7	806.7	807	807	807	P	
RUN 3										
12:20:10		FL320		1.75	2.5	3.5	4.25	5.5		
12:20:50			22.7	0.48	0.72	1.05			S	PEAK NOT FOUND ON 2
			22.10	1370	1209	1315			D	PEAK NOT FOUND ON 5
				1208	1142	1165			B	
				2023	2030	2042			R	END OF RUN
				785	785	785			P	BEFORE SAMPLE COMPLETE
RUN 4										
12:37:35		FL330	22.1	0.49	0.71	1.08	1.41	2.07	S	PEAK NOT FOUND ON 1
12:38:30			21.5	1146	1970	1252	1525	1656	D	1, 5
				1187	1098	1141	1169	1221	B	
				2027	2049	2061	2052	2050	R	PK ON: 2, 3, 4
				773	773	773	773	773	P	
RUN 15										
12:51:00		FL340	21.0	0.49	0.72	1.11	1.39	2.02	S	PEAK NOT FOUND
12:51:52			24.2	1250	1157	1680	1474	1250	D	ON 1, 2, 3, 4, 5
				1094	1001	1032	1044	1127	B	
				2050	2055	2051	2045	2050	R	
				760	760	760	761	761	P	
RUN 16										
13:18:00	13:14:05	FL350	18.9	0.51	0.72	1.08	1.40	2.03	S	PEAK NOT FOUND ON
			24.7	890	1069	1357	1107	1035	D	1, 2, 4
				1024	862	925	969	1042	B	
				2048	2048	2053	2061	2067	R	OK ON 3, 5
				751	750.7	751.2	751.6	750.8	P	

WAS Sampling Summary

Flight Number: B115

Campaign Name: CIRRUS

Date: 22/07/2005

Operator: M. Neilsdottir (UEA)

Bottle Start Fill Time	Bottle End Fill Time	Bottle Number	Comments	Final Pressure (bar)
11:50:57	11:51:57	16	Run 1 (FL 280)	2.35
11:54:32	11:55:32	17	Run 1 (FL 280)	2.35
12:06:48	12:07:48	18	Run 1.2 (FL300)	2.31
12:09:45	12:10:45	19	Run 1.2 (FL300)	2.32
12:23:19	12:24:19	20	Run 1.3 (FL320); Crystals observed by Cpi	2.03
12:26:36	12:27:36	21	Run 1.3 (FL320); Crystals observed by Cpi	2.04
12:39:20	12:40:20	22	Run 1.4 (FL330) above cloud	1.90
12:42:40	12:43:40	23	Run 1.4 (FL330) above cloud	1.94
12:52:07	12:53:07	24	Run 1.5 (FL 340) High ozone	
12:55:06	12:56:06	25	Run 1.5 (FL 340) High ozone	1.90
13:15:22	13:16:22	26	Run 1.6 (FL350) In Cloud	1.69
13:19:11	13:20:11	27	Run 1.6 (FL350) In Cloud	
13:29:10	13:30:10	28	Run 1.7 (FL330)	1.97
13:31:36	13:32:36	29	Run 1.7 (FL330)	1.96
13:43:13	13:45:13	30	Run 1.8 (FL310)	2.27
13:54:38	13:56:38	31	Run 1.9 (FL290)	2.40
13:57:08	13:59:08	32	Run 1.9 (FL290)	2.30
14:15:54	14:16:54	57	Run 1.10 (FL270)	2.46
14:20:01	14:21:01	58	Run 1.10 (FL270)	2.47

AMS PreFlight Setup/Cal Sheet v2.00

DATE: 22/7/05

FLIGHT: B115

OPERATOR: GC

①

Time: ^{GMT} 0645	Action:	Location:	Yes/No:	Notes	Comments:	
Power ON	Ensure Inlet Closed	Inlet Valve	✓			
	Ensure Multiplier Off	Electronics box	✓			
	Ensure Heater Off	Electronics box	✓			
	Ensure all Pumps Off	Pump Control box	✓			
	Turn on 230V Breaker	Power unit on a/c wall	✓			
	Turn on:	Electronics box power Diaphragm pump power Turbo pump power CPC Power, both Buttons	Power distribution box	✓ ✓ ✓ ✓		
	Open backing pump valve	Front facing side of rack.	✓			
	Turn on Alcatel... 100% speed	Pump Control Box, after #6	✓	Monitor Pump Currents	Currents all low Total ≈ 3A of 7A typical	
	Turbo pumps 2 and 3 ON... 100%	Pump Control Box	✓			
	Turbo pumps 4 and 5 ON... 100%	Pump Control Box	✓			
Turbo pump 6 ON... 100%	Pump Control Box	✓				
Plug in CPC fill bottle	Rear of CPC	✓				
Turn on heater	Electronics box	✓	Approx 2.8V, 0.9A	2.4V, 0.9A		
Pre-Brief	Turn on Balzers Box	Power distribution box and Balzers box	✓			
	Turn on Copper	Electronics box	✓	Approx 125Hz ✓		
	Turn on PC/Monitor	Power distribution box and PC	✓			
	Start AMS software	PC Desktop	✓			
	Turn autosaving off	Parameter menu, Averaging and saving tab	✓	NEGATIVE NUMBER		
	Reduce Multiplier voltage by 0.5kV	Parameter menu, Multiplier and chopper tab	✓			
	Set filament to 0.00mA, Scan range 0-300amu	Parameter menu, Mass Spectrometer tab	✓			
	Turn Multiplier on	Electronics box	✓			
	Turn filament on @0.05mA	MS mode, shift+B, click emission arrow	✓			

AMS Calibration Log Sheet v2.00

DATE: 22/7/05 FLIGHT: B115

OPERATOR: G.C.

Tuning

TIME:	Old	New	Typical
Def Inner	30	30	22
Def Outer	16	15	11
Heater Bias	-6.94	-6.87	-6.5
Focus	15.50	15.50	12.5
Extraction	236	226	220

TIME:	Old	New	Typical
Def Inner			22
Def Outer			11
Heater Bias			-6.5
Focus			12.5
Extraction			220

on screen dumps - see post-flight checks .ppt file.

Multiplier Cal

Might have to tweak filament current and multiplier voltage in order to set thresholds in calibration!!!!
This is done in the parameter menu..... Multiplier and Chopper Tab

TIME:	New	Typical
KV	2.475	n/a
KV Change	-0.025	0.025kV
Gain	3.06×10^6	3.00E+06
G used Change	$\times 1.04$	1

TIME:	New	Typical
KV		n/a
KV Change		0.025kV
Gain		3.00E+06
G used Change		1

Ionization Efficiency Cal

TIME:	New	Typical
IE (NO3)		2.00E-06
RIE (NH4)		4
IPP NO3		400
IPP NH4		550
Airbeam MS		2.20E+06
Airbeam TOF		2.00E+06
Run Number		n/a

TIME:	New	Typical
IE (NO3)	2.348×10^{-6}	2.00E-06
RIE (NH4)	3.992	4
IPP NO3	544.52	400
IPP NH4	619.95	550
Airbeam MS	2.69×10^6	2.20E+06
Airbeam TOF	2.20×10^6	2.00E+06
Run Number	3840	n/a

Filter Run

TIME:	11:03
Run number	3155

TIME:	14:52
Run number	3596 3596

AMS Diagnostic Log Sheet v2.00

DATE: 22/7/05 FLIGHT: 8115

OPERATOR: GC

Time 11:14
GMT

Pump #	I(A)	I (typical)	Speed (%)	Speed typical
1/Alcatel	3.80	0.86	88	98
2	3.0	3.5	100	100
3	1.3	1	100	100
4	0.6	0.5	100	100
5	0.4	0.4	100	100
6	0.43	0.46	100	100

	New	Typical
Heater V	2.81	2.5
Heater I	0.92	0.9
Heater T	585	580
Heater B	72.6	75V
Multiplier	2.475	n/a
Pressure	1.44	2 Torr

	New	Typical
I electronics	1	1A
I turbo	7	7A
I diaphragm	1.2	2A
MS AB	2.00	2.2Mhz
TOF AB	1.77	2Mhz
Flow	1.51	2

Time 12:45

14:00 - No significant changes

Pump #	I(A)	I (typical)	Speed (%)	Speed typical
1/Alcatel	0.74	0.86	89	98
2	2.12	3.5	100	100
3	1.13	1	100	100
4	0.60	0.5	100	100
5	0.41	0.4	100	100
6	0.41	0.46	100	100

	New	Typical
Heater V	2.80	2.5
Heater I	0.92	0.9
Heater T	585	580
Heater B	72.6	75V
Multiplier	2.475	n/a
Pressure	0.73	2 Torr

	New	Typical
I electronics	1.0	1A
I turbo	5.5	7A
I diaphragm	1.2	2A
MS AB	1.33	2.2Mhz
TOF AB	1.24	2Mhz
Flow	0.612	2

Time 1445

Pump #	I(A)	I (typical)	Speed (%)	Speed typical
1/Alcatel	0.71	0.86	92	98
2	2.69	3.5	100	100
3	1.23	1	100	100
4	0.57	0.5	100	100
5	0.41	0.4	100	100
6	0.41	0.46	100	100

	New	Typical
Heater V	2.84	2.5
Heater I	0.92	0.9
Heater T	591	580
Heater B	72.6	75V
Multiplier	2.475	n/a
Pressure	1.140	2 Torr

	New	Typical
I electronics	1	1A
I turbo	6	7A
I diaphragm	1.2	2A
MS AB	1.8	2.2Mhz
TOF AB	1.02	2Mhz
Flow	1.114	2

Time

Pump #	I(A)	I (typical)	Speed (%)	Speed typical
1/Alcatel		0.86		98
2		3.5		100
3		1		100
4		0.5		100
5		0.4		100
6		0.46		100

	New	Typical
Heater V		2.5
Heater I		0.9
Heater T		580
Heater B		75V
Multiplier		n/a
Pressure		2 Torr

	New	Typical
I electronics		1A
I turbo		7A
I diaphragm		2A
MS AB		2.2Mhz
TOF AB		2Mhz
Flow		2

AMS PostFlight Setup/Cal Sheet v2.00

DATE: 22/7/05

FLIGHT: B115

OPERATOR: G.C.

Time:	Action:	Location:	Yes/No:	Notes	Comments:
Pre-land	Stop AMS, Grimm CPC logging	Software	✓		
	Close AMS inlet	Inlet	✓		
	Exit Labview		✓		
	Enable CPC in AMS software	Parameter Menu, Serial Ports tab	✓		
Post-land	Set CPC in Low Flow	Shift+totalizer on CPC display	✓		
	Open Inlet		✓		
	Turn off autosave (-ve number)	Parameter Menu, Averaging and saving tab	✓		
	Set mass range scan 0-300	Parameter menu, Mass Spectrometer tab	✓		
	Electron Multiplier Cal	Software, select suitable point manually	✓	Check gain at current V	
	Get tof masses for IE cal	Software, m/z selection, left click on row	✓	15, 16, 17, 30, 46*	
	Set thresholds In tof mode	Left click "SP thresholds" in left border	✓	wait	
	Mass Range Cal	MS mode, Click Mass Calibration	✓		
	Add m28 to tof list	Software, m/z selection, left click on row	✓		
	Run in MS-TOF alteration	Software	✓	Check tof windows	
	IE cal after 200 particles	Shift+M while sampling, Calibrate, Save, Exit	✓	SMPS s=4.1, a=0.41, 350nm	
	Attach Zero filter to inlet				} Taken care of in last filter run concerning in to (land.)
	Select tof masses to scan	Software, m/z selection, left click on row		14, 16, 30, 43, 44, 46, 48, 57	
	Set thresholds In tof mode	Left click "SP thresholds" in left border			
	Add m28 to tof list	Software, m/z selection, left click on row			
General alteration, 10 mins	Software, F3 to NonAutoSave		Check tof windows		
Close inlet			✓		
Data	Copy AutoSaveData folder	Source C:\AMS\AMSDData\AutoSaveDate Dest C:\AMS\SAMSDData\Summer05\flight	✓		
	Copy NonAutoSaveData folder	Source C:\AMS\AMSDData\NonAutoSaveDate Dest C:\AMS\SAMSDData\Summer05\flight	✓		
	Copy AMSLogFiles folder	Source C:\AMS\AMSDData\AMSLogFiles Dest C:\AMS\SAMSDData\Summer05\flight	✓		
	Copy CPC data	Source C:\UCPC\ Dest C:\AMS\SAMSDData\Summer05\flight	✓		
	Backup directory to DVD/laptop		✓		
	Delete AutoSaveData	Source C:\AMS\AMSDData\AutoSaveDate	✓	FILES ONLY, NOT FOLDER	
	Delete NonAutoSaveData	Source C:\AMS\AMSDData\AutoSaveDate	✓	FILES ONLY, NOT FOLDER	
	Delete AMSLogFiles	Source C:\AMS\AMSDData\AutoSaveDate	✓	FILES ONLY, NOT FOLDER	
	Delete CPC data	Source C:\AMS\AMSDData\AutoSaveDate	✓	FILES ONLY, NOT FOLDER	
	ShutDown	Turn off Multplier & Balzers	Electronics box	✓	
Turn off all Turbos and PC		Pump Controller Box	✓		
Shut Backing Valve		Back of rack	✓		
Turn off heater, chopper, the rest		Electronics box, then power unit and Breakers	✓		

Flight Manager's Instrument Status Log

Flight No. **B114**

Date: 21/07/05

Instrument	Fitted	Operated	Instrument	Fitted	Operated
<u>Navigation</u>			<u>Cloud Physics</u>		
INU		Y	Probes		
XR5M GPS		Y	FFSSP		Y
Cruciform GPS		Y	PCASP		Y
Satcom C		Y	2D-P		Y
Satcom H		Y	2D-C		Y
<u>Thermometers</u>			Cloudscope	N	N
De-Iced Temp		Y	SID 1	N	
Non De-Iced		Y	SID 2	y	N
Heimann	N		HVPS	N	
<u>Hygrometers</u>			CIP25	Y	N
G. Eastern		Y	CIP100	Y	N
J. Williams		Y			
Nevzorov		Y			
TWC		Y			
FWVS	Y	N	Racks:		
<u>Radiometers</u>			INC	Y	N
Upper Clear	Y	Y	CCN / CNC		Y
“ Red	Y	Y	CVI		N
“ Silicon	Y	Y			
“ JO1D	Y	Y	<u>Aerosol</u>		
Lower Clear	Y	Y	PSAP	Y	N
“ Red	Y	Y	Nephelometer	N	
“ Silicon	Y	Y	Filters	Y	Y
“ JO1D	N		AMS	Y	Y
<u>Large Radiometers</u>					
TAFTS	N				
MARSS	N				
DEIMOS	N		<u>Others:</u>		
ARIES	N		NIR TDLAS	Y	N
SWS	N		2BT O3	Y	N
<u>Chemistry</u>			VACC	Y	N
Ozone	Y	Y	PEROXIDE	Y	N
SO	Y	Y	Formaldehyde	Y	N
NOX	Y	Y	ADA	Y	N
CO	Y	Y	CPI	Y	N
ORAC	Y	N	NOxy	Y	N
PAN	Y	N	PTRMS	Y	N
PERCA	N	N	Bag Sampling	Y	N
WAS	Y	N			

Faults / Incidents Log

Flight No. B115

Date: 22/07/05

Instruments

1. Starboard forward Hub u/s
2. SO₂ and Ozone exhaust pipes have kinks where they join the ASP exhaust manifold.

Aircraft

Nil

MISSING LOG SHEETS:

The following logs are not available for flight B115:

Log	Reason
De-brief	Sortie De-brief yet to be created by Keith Bower
ADA/CPI	No log taken or no copy left with FAAM
NOxy	No log is ever taken for NOxy
PTrMS	No log is ever taken for PTrMS
SID2	No log was taken for SID2

VIDEO RECORDINGS:

2 x Forward Facing Cameras
2 x Rearward Facing Cameras

8mm video recordings from this flight reside with :
Digital8 video recordings from this flight reside with :
8mm video recordings from this flight reside with FAAM (at 31 Oct 2005) :
Digital8 video recordings from this flight reside with FAAM (at 31 Oct 2005) :

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